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Influence of Entrepreneurship Education on Career Aspiration of Business Education Students in Higher Institutions in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

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ABSTRACT

The study examined influence of entrepreneurship education on the career aspiration of Business Education students in higher institutions in Port Harcourt metropolis. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. The population of the study consisted of 200 Level and 300 Level students in the Faculty of Education in two universities offering Business Education programme, with a population of 565. The sampling technique used was a census method of sampling. The population size of 565 students were used as the sample size due to the manageability of the population size. The instrument for data collection was a researcher--structured questionnaire titled 'Influence of Entrepreneurship Education on Career Aspiration of Students Questionnaire'. The research questions were answered using frequency counts and weighted mean; and the hypotheses tested using z-test statistics at the 0.05 level of significance. The results showed that the exploration of innovative ideas and application of new technology influenced the career aspiration of Business Education students in higher institutions in Port Harcourt metropolis to a high extent. Furthermore, there was no significant difference between the respondents in Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent to which innovative ideas and new technology influenced the career aspiration of Business Education students in higher institutions in Port Harcourt metropolis. Based on the findings, it was recommended that counsellors in higher institutions should target the students for group counselling to encourage them in the use of innovative ideas and new technology in promoting entrepreneurship programmes; and the government should train more teachers and provide funds for more innovative programmes to increase the students' entrepreneurship knowledge and skills.

Keywords: Business education students, career aspiration, entrepreneurship education, Innovative ideas

INTRODUCTION

Self-employment and small business efforts are now high in Nigeria's national agenda due to the country's skyrocketing unemployment rate, with the expectation that they may offer alternative job routes. Thousands of graduates from universities enter the workforce each year in pursuit of productive work. Thus, the task is to both address the sizable number of graduates who are unemployed and integrate separate to the workforce. This predicament stems from the fact that postsecondary education has not been entirely successful in providing students with the necessary skills and abilities to create jobs and

engage in self-employment (Madumere-Obike,2016). The National Universities Commission (NUC) held a workshop on entrepreneurship education for Nigerian universities as a way forward in July 2004 to address the shortcomings of the curricula in addressing the employment crisis. A proposed entrepreneurship studies curriculum for Nigerian universities was created during the NUC session. As a result, a number of universities have started offering entrepreneurship education programs to students in an attempt to give them the essential training in entrepreneurial skills and buck the trend of growing graduate unemployment to launch enterprises and think of self-employment as a realistic career alternative (Amaewhule, 2017).

Nwangwu (2017) stated that the teacher's deliberate participation in a student's life in order to support their success in the business world is known as entrepreneurship education. Teaching students how to create a business plan is how it largely embodies its focus and action orientation (Ronstadt, 2015). The process of launching new businesses is developed and stimulated by entrepreneurship education, which also supplies the required resources. It is often believed that entrepreneurship education is crucial for developing people's entrepreneurial orientation and assisting them in gaining the abilities, bravery, confidence, drive, and inventiveness required to launch their own companies and hire staff members. These days, "entrepreneurship education" encompasses any kind of knowledge transfer intended to empower the person to create real wealth in the economy, therefore advancing the goal of national development. The goal of entrepreneurship education, according to Bassey and Archibong (2015), is to give graduates—regardless of their area of expertise—the abilities they need to engage in revenue-generating businesses in the event that they are unable to find work in the public sector. It's a change from seeking employment to producing it. Entrepreneurship is the process of forming, developing, and running a new firm, usually a small one at first. "Entrepreneurs" are the folks who start these companies. Momoh (2015) emphasised that the definition of entrepreneurship is the ability and willingness to create, plan, and oversee a new enterprise, with all associated risks, with the goal of turning a profit.

According to Cotton, O'Gorman & Stampfi (2010), the justification for entrepreneurship curricula in universities is that they will enable graduates to gain a deeper comprehension of entrepreneurship, give them an entrepreneurial mindset when entering the workforce, and prepare them for roles as managers and entrepreneurs in start-up companies. Accordingly, the European Union (2012) briefly outlined the goals of entrepreneurship education as follows: encourage the growth of personal qualities that are important for entrepreneurship, such as creativity, willingness to take risks, and accountability; increase learners' awareness of self-employment as a career option (the idea being that you are both an employer and an employee); and provide the business and technical skills required to launch a new company. Based on the aforementioned, it can be inferred that university students who are exposed to entrepreneurial education will be more driven to start their own businesses and, when presented well, may play a major role in reducing unemployment among graduates.

Concept of Career Aspiration

Career ambitions are an individual's long-term professional goals and objectives, encompassing the desired outcomes and personal growth they want to achieve along the way. Career ambitions are long-term goals and expectations (Ronstadt, 2015). Their unique experiences mould them, affecting skills, morals, lifestyle, and other aspects. Working in a field you are passionate about might be one example of a career aim. However, as the main objectives of new venture formation are to reduce unemployment, innovate, and get access to the outside world, we focus on the three main facets of entrepreneurial aspirations: rapid growth, internationalisation, and innovation (Simon, 2014).

One's long-term professional goals and intended career routes are referred to as career ambitions. Employers will look at a candidate's predicted career path when evaluating them for a new position, whether it be as an intern or in management. The goal is to evaluate if the candidate will be a suitable match for the role. (Duck, 2013). As such, it is crucial to think through how one would react to this standard question about future objectives and career aspirations when preparing for an interview. In contrast to immediate, short-term professional goals, aims, and/or ambitions, the term "career aspirations" refers to long-range, distant ones. In order to get to know candidates and learn about their objectives and

professional ambitions, employers frequently enquire about candidates' future career plans. As a result, over the course of their professional growth, their training and job decisions should ideally represent their long-term professional goals.

Concept of Entrepreneurship Education

In order to cultivate the mindset of a person who will take on the responsibilities and risk of running a business with the hope of making profit, entrepreneurship education encompasses all awareness, teaching, training, and support activities in the field of entrepreneurship. Typically, the entrepreneur chooses the product, buys the space, and gathers the resources—labor, money, and raw materials for manufacturing. The business owner receives earnings if the venture is successful; if not, they bear the loss.

Amaewhule (2017) opines that entrepreneurship education tends to be more innovative among the students than the average people. The capacity to find new things or new methods of doing things while looking for new chances is known as innovativeness. According to Duck (2013), entrepreneurs are constantly looking for solutions to solve issues or try out new concepts. They are creative and believe that such creativity and innovation if encouraged can be rewarding in the future. That is why it is strongly believed that the presence of small businesses tends to stimulate developmental activities in the form of being centers and sources of innovative ideas and sources of innovation.

Simon (2014) also opines that entrepreneurship education helps learners to develop skill in decision-making. Traditionally, the teaching of entrepreneurship has been seen rather narrowly, mostly as teaching different skills in business. More recently, the interpretation has extended, and entrepreneurial way of acting has become more and more familiar in the curricula. Also, the ever-increasing demand on entrepreneurship, conscious teachers have further increased the need for enterprise education. The education contains issues on entrepreneurship and research of specific teaching methods appropriate for entrepreneurial studies. Bird (2019) thought that any graduate with a strong desire to support social development and a hunch to expand their knowledge, talents, and skills in the areas of leading social development projects, starting their own company, or becoming consultants or resource persons.

Concept of Innovative ideas and New Technology

Adopting innovation in the classroom fosters critical thinking, a spirit of adventure, and an openness to change in order to better serve our children. It will provide them the self-assurance and adaptability they need to keep going while giving them the resources they need to handle the challenges of their future careers. We can comprehend topics more fully when we innovate and use our creativity. Schools cultivate thinkers who can utilise their own abilities to pursue their different interests by employing a creative, experimental approach to education (Allen, 2012). According to Allen (2012), using these creative techniques early on is crucial for developing young learners' ability to think freely and imaginatively in the future. It is crucial to create an educational system that encourages and develops students' creativity since innovative thinking and flexibility are prerequisites for success outside of the classroom. An atmosphere that uses creativity to boost student engagement and promote interactive lessons is the most successful one. Pupils are more likely to learn new things and be creative when they have the correct balance of creativity and curriculum. To become proficient communicators, students can improve their social and communication abilities. Learning in creative classrooms may change if students are given the opportunity to apply what they have taught in real-world situations (Noel, 2011). A student's capacity for creative expression has a role in how their emotions grow. Originality is the first prerequisite for an inventive idea, and this does not imply enhancing an already-existing concept with your own unique twist. It entails developing a novel concept that presents a fresh perspective to the market. One example of innovation is the way that young people are revolutionising the traditional educational system by prioritising devices over books and ideas over words (Momoh, 2015).

New Technology

Technology may help you develop professionally and highlight your accomplishments and abilities in addition to being a tool for job searching and application. It entails understanding how to leverage technology in the ever-evolving workplace and integrate it into your portfolio and professional development strategy. Technology may assist a person in doing this by offering online programs,

certificates, badges, and courses that can help you obtain new qualifications, abilities, and knowledge. These possibilities can be used to upgrade current abilities, pick up new ones, or focus on a particular area of expertise. Bird (2013), outlined how fundamental and applied research frequently produces valuable technology, but understanding the technology transfer process is necessary to appreciate and capitalise on this knowledge. The entrepreneurial education course gives students ideas for creating, managing, and transferring intellectual property. With a focus on entrepreneurial online organisations and business strategies, it offers a basic knowledge of how the internet is transforming the way businesses operate. Presenting the ideas they have learnt in the classroom and seeing how successful business owners create the organisation they possess as entrepreneurs provide students invaluable experience.

Entrepreneurship Education and Students' Career Aspiration

Education in entrepreneurship places equal emphasis on practical as well as academic topics. Students studying business education will thus also have the necessary foresight, training, experiences, and backing to actively participate in the entrepreneurial sector. Furthermore, the process of deciding to start and maintain an entrepreneurial business is known as career intention in the context of entrepreneurship (Bird, 2019). Additionally, according to Bird, having an entrepreneurial goal is a mindset that involves launching a new business and rejecting the conventional professional route that isn't feasible. Students are becoming more and more interested in careers in entrepreneurship throughout the globe. Owusu-Adasah (2014) had shown that growing knowledge of entrepreneurship education is causing a slow decline in interest in traditional professional jobs in large businesses. According to Allen (2012), there has been a rise in interest in entrepreneurial occupations and education since 1985. This rise has been attributed to a number of factors, including the perception that most large organisational structures do not offer a conducive atmosphere for attaining goals and starting new businesses, the understanding that small businesses are crucial to innovation and job creation, and increased media attention to entrepreneurs. It is also recognised that the sheer number of little cottage firms that are founded each year makes up a much larger number of entrepreneurs than those featured in the media (Allen, 2012).

China (2016) said that despite this rise, a lot of people do not think of entrepreneurship as a vocation, especially college students. In contrast, Duck (2013) sees career phases as dynamic, each stage of the person's life reflecting and interacting with past, present, and future occurrences. If this is accurate, institutions will be significantly impacted. Training programs aimed at improving the creative and management process should be developed. When it comes to training and teaching factors that shape ideas about the acceptability and viability of entrepreneurial conduct, education is crucial to the growth of entrepreneurship. The focus of entrepreneurship programs should be on the learning environment, the personalities of the participants, their career history, their present work environment, and their current perspectives. The reasons for this are that the orientations and behaviours of students and recent graduates are shaped by a multitude of internal and external factors, including financial resources, the desirability of working for oneself, the ability to manage and cope with risk, preconceived notions about working for oneself, and many more. China (2016) discovered that having entrepreneurs on campus encouraged students to pursue an entrepreneurial career. Begley (2017) found that the social status of entrepreneurial situations and activities was significant, and that there was a statistical relationship between the degree of intent to be entrepreneurs and the amount of management courses taken by students took classes in other programs. This highlights the beneficial influence that students' opinions of entrepreneurship as a career option have, as well as the function that resources and other forms of assistance within the academic setting have. There are lots of entrepreneurial activities going on in the tertiary institutions these days. For example, some students have barbing salons, tailoring/fashion design shops, provision stores, food canteens, laundries, computer centers, Internet cafes, and many others.

Theoretical Review

Human Capital Entrepreneurship Theory by Gary Becker, 1960

Human capital entrepreneurship theory is based mostly on two elements, specifically training and experience. The concept holds that knowledge acquired via education and experience is seen as a resource

that is distributed differentially across individuals and establishes the basis for understanding variations in opportunity recognition and take-up. According to Anderson and Miller (2013), human capital considerations are beneficial to emerging and embryonic businesses. This suggests that the human capital theory of entrepreneurship, which is especially pertinent to the setting of entrepreneurship education, lays the groundwork for the role that education plays in the growth of entrepreneurship (Chandler & Hanks, 2018). This according to Anderson and Miller (2013) suggests that a major part of an entrepreneurship program's components is to enhance the development of skills related to successful entrepreneurial results hence this theory is related to this study.

Empirical Review

Entrepreneurship Education and Promotion of Exploration of Innovative Ideas among Students

Gibb (2018) noted that a positive relationship appears to exist between perceived barriers and students' aspirations to start their own business. Gibb also carried out a survey which indicated that entrepreneurship education prevents exploration and innovative ideas among the students if not for lack of finance, knowledge and skills. Israel (2015) carried out a study on individual enterprise, and concluded that students should examine the traits of self-initiative or the skill of job success. He said in particular that students must acquire the abilities necessary to progress in a workplace or educational setting that is always changing. Students should specifically acquire capabilities in long-term planning, decision-making, effective communication, accountability, responsibility, and ongoing education. Students studying business education should create business proposals that may be evaluated as parallel career paths. Higher education institutions must always look for new ways to spur economic development and support appropriate institution-building and collaboration in order to speed up institutional environmental development. This is because there are mechanisms in place that could be utilised to leverage resources to support the expansion of both existing and potential businesses and to give entrepreneurs more options. Many environmental and personal factors impact the direction and conduct of young graduates and students in business education. Students are encouraged to pursue careers in entrepreneurship, for instance, by the presence of entrepreneurs at postsecondary schools. Johnson (2011) emphasised the beneficial effects of students' impressions of entrepreneurship as a possible career path. He discovered that entrepreneurship education serves as a means of instructing students on how to identify a need or issue in company and come up with a solution.

Entrepreneurship Education and Application of New Technology among Students

In another study, Simon (2014), discovered that technological innovation and entrepreneurship gave people the information, abilities, contacts, and resources they needed to start a business, encourage innovation in an already-existing organisation, or provide long-lasting solutions to significant social issues. He said that technological innovation challenges the globe by altering job trajectories, upending old sectors, and producing new knowledge. Applying new technology teaches you through first-hand experience how to recognise opportunities, generate ideas, validate operations, influence others, bring cutting-edge innovations to market, launch and grow new ventures, and ultimately adapt and thrive in the face of rapid change.

Previous research (Noel, 2011; Momoh, 2015; Kolvereid & Moen, 2017) has shown a substantial association between career objectives and entrepreneurial education. For instance, a study conducted in 2017 by Kolvereid and Moen revealed that students majoring in entrepreneurship are more inclined to launch their own companies and have a stronger goal or intention to become entrepreneurs. Noel (2011) found in another study that graduates in entrepreneurship scored higher than graduates in other fields in terms of both entrepreneurial intent and entrepreneurial self-efficacy. In a similar vein, Momoh's (2015) research revealed a relationship between the proportion of students who become business owners and the sum of money that academic institutions spend promoting entrepreneurship. Additional research by Allen (2012) discovered that entrepreneurship education fosters a favourable perception of entrepreneurs and influences graduates' decision to pursue entrepreneurship as a career alternative. Begley (2017) discovered that teaching pupils about entrepreneurship might also heighten their interest in the field as a

profession.

In an international research on entrepreneurial motivation among students studying business education, Weihe and Reich (2013) discovered that 34.3% of those surveyed expressed an unwavering interest in working for themselves. According to the report, 6% of American students are currently self-employed. In a similar vein, Gibb's (2018) research shown that the Entrepreneurship Training Programme (ETP) might raise students' inclinations to work for themselves. Owusu-Ansah (2014) 77.9% of survey respondents said they were driven to establish businesses to a considerable or very large amount, according to a study on the effect of entrepreneurship education on career goals and ambitions of university students in Ghana. The results also revealed that 86.7% of survey participants believed they have the knowledge and abilities necessary to launch and manage their own companies. Using a sample of 690 students from three institutions, Bassey and Olu (2018) looked at the relationship between graduate self-employment potential and students' perceptions of university entrepreneurship education in Nigeria. The results demonstrated a significant correlation between students' perceptions of the tertiary entrepreneurship education provided by university administrations, the curriculum objectives, the instructional methods, the quantity and quality of tertiary entrepreneurship education instructors, and the entrepreneurial traits and potential for self-employment of graduates. at light of this, the study looked at how students at Rivers State's higher education institutions assessed the impact of entrepreneurship education on their career goals.

Statement of the Problem

The Nigerian society has come to the realization that in addition to the career choices made by students in the higher institutions of learning, skills acquisition is also an added advantage if graduates must utilize their education to their own benefit instead of waiting for white collar jobs. The significance of acquiring skills cannot be overstated, since the unemployment of Nigerian university graduates has emerged as a significant national issue. Graduates are becoming increasingly frustrated with the lengthening time between graduation and job dates. It is evident that self-employment is the only practical choice under the given circumstances. Nowadays, the majority of colleges have launched entrepreneurship education programs in the aim of providing graduates with the know-how needed to launch their own companies and become job creators rather than job seekers. This is in response to the Federal Government of Nigeria's directions to all post-secondary educational institutions to provide courses in entrepreneurship education in order to improve the graduates' ability to acquire the skills necessary for self-employment. This paper therefore examined influence of entrepreneurship education on career aspirations of students in higher institutions in Port Harcourt metropolis Rivers State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to examine the influence of entrepreneurship education on career aspirations of students in higher institutions in Port Harcourt metropolis.. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the extent to which acquisition of ideas through entrepreneurship influence career aspirations of Business Education students' in higher institutions in Port Harcourt metropolis, Rivers State.
2. Examine the extent to which knowledge of application of new technology through entrepreneurship influence career aspirations of Business Education students' in higher institutions in Port Harcourt metropolis, Rivers State.

Research Questions

Based on the purpose of the study, the following research questions were formulated to facilitate the investigation and to ensure achievement of the stated objectives:

1. To what extent does the acquisition of ideas through entrepreneurship influence the career aspiration of Business Education students in higher institutions in Port Harcourt metropolis?
2. To what extent does the knowledge of application of new technology through entrepreneurship influence the career aspiration of Business Education students in higher institutions in Port Harcourt metropolis?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated to direct the study:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean rating of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Business Education students on the extent to which the acquisition of ideas through entrepreneurship influence the career aspiration of students in higher institutions in Port Harcourt metropolis
2. There is no significant difference in the mean rating of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Business Education students on the extent to which the knowledge of application of new technology through entrepreneurship influence the career aspiration of students' in higher institutions in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

METHODOLOGY

Descriptive survey design was employed for the study. Five hundred and sixty-five (565) students from the Faculty of Education, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, and Rivers State University made up the study's population in Years 2 and 3. The sample method that was employed was the census method. Consequently, due to the manageable population size of 565 students, the complete population size was utilised for the sample size. The two universities were selected out of three in Port Harcourt metropolis for having Business Education programme. Furthermore, the number comprised 425 students from Ignatius Ajuru University of Education and 140 students from Rivers State University, Port Harcourt respectively. This number comprised 272 Year 2 students and 293 Year 3 students. The instrument used for data collection in this study was a researcher-structured questionnaire titled 'Influence of Entrepreneurship Education on Career Aspirations of Students' Questionnaire' The instrument was made up of two sections. Section A consisted of the demographic variables of the respondents and Section B contained 10 items (five statements related to innovative ideas and career aspiration; and the other five on the application of new technology and career aspiration). The items were rated using the four point rating scale, i.e. Very High Extent (VHE) - 4, High Extent (HE) - 3, Low Extent (LE) - 2 and Very Low Extent (VLE) - 1. The questionnaire was given to an expert and two additional lecturer from measurement and evaluation specialists at Rivers State University Port Harcourt's Faculty of Education in order to assess the instrument's face and content validity as well as to solicit their corrections and input. The Cronbach's Alpha was employed to assess the instrument's dependability. With the assistance of two research assistants who were specifically hired and trained for the task, the researcher administered the questionnaire. The 565 copies of the questionnaire were distributed to the respondents and retrieved. Frequency counts and weighted mean scores for the study questions were used to examine the data gathered from the respondents. The criterion Mean was set at a limit of 2.5. Thus, any mean that was 2.50 or higher was considered to be High Extent, while any mean that was lower was considered to be Low Extent. The z-test statistical technique was utilised to test the hypotheses at the significance level of 0.05.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *To what extent does exploration of innovative ideas influence career aspirations of students' in higher institutions in Port Harcourt metropolis?*

Table 1: Mean responses of RSU and IAUE students on the extent to which exploration of Innovative Ideas influence the Career Aspiration of Business Education Students in Higher Institutions in Port Harcourt Metropolis

S/No A	Item	RSU Students (N = 140)			IAUE Student (N = 425)		
		Mean	SD	Remark	Mean	SD	Remark
1.	Innovative ideas helps Business Education students to develop knowledge and skills for starting their own businesses.	3.01	0.87	High Extent	2.99	0.86	High Extent
2.	It promotes exploration of new ideas among the students.	3.11	0.82	High Extent	2.87	0.85	High Extent
3.	Innovative ideas give them knowledge and skills for solving problems in relationship management.	3.20	0.89	High Extent	3.19	0.89	High Extent
4.	It helps students to explore qualitative individual enterprise which enables them to become entrepreneurs.	3.04	0.87	High Extent	3.02	0.87	High Extent
5.	Acquisition of innovative ideas educate and motivate students in developing skills in financial management.	3.01	0.87	High Extent	2.99	0.86	High Extent
Grand Mean Score		3.07	0.88	HE	3.01	0.87	HE

Source: Field Data 2023.

Table 1 shows that the respondents accepted all the statements, from item 1 – 5, implying that due to the acquisition of innovative ideas, students were able to develop knowledge and skills for starting their own businesses; it promotes new ideas among the students; it gives them knowledge for solving relationship management; students explore qualitative individual enterprise which enables them to become entrepreneurs; it educates and motivates students in developing skills in financial management. All the items from 1-5 have mean values of 3.01, 3.11, 3.20, 3.04, and 3.01 respectively. Also, the grand mean of 3.07 and 3.01 respectively shows that both respondents from the Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education accepted the fact that Business Education students utilized innovative ideas, which influenced their career aspiration in the higher institutions in Port Harcourt metropolis.to a high extent.

Research Question Two: *To what extent does the application of new technology influence the career aspiration of Business Education students in higher institutions in Port Harcourt metropolis?*

Table 2: Mean responses of RSU and IAUE students on the extent to which the Application of New Technology Influence Career Aspiration of Business Education Students in Higher Institutions Port Harcourt Metropolis

S/No B	Item	RSU Students (N = 140)			IAUE Students (N = 425)		
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
6.	knowledge gained from new technology provides Business Education students with good knowledge of ICT in teaching and learning.	3.20	0.89	High Extent	3.14	0.89	High Extent
7.	Knowledge of new technology education provides the students with the basic foundation of information in becoming management technologists.	3.12	0.88	High Extent	3.04	0.87	High Extent
8.	New technology helps in providing fundamental understanding of the internet and helps students to develop skills in becoming data analysts.	3.17	0.89	High Extent	3.19	0.89	High Extent
9.	Knowledge about new technology helps students to use the latest technological machines	3.01	0.87	High Extent	2.99	0.86	High Extent
10.	New technology enables students to develop skills in the use of computer.	3.11	0.88	High Extent	2.87	0.85	High Extent
Grand Mean Score		3.12	0.88	HE	3.05	0.87	HE

Source: Field Data 2023.

Table 2 shows that the respondents accepted all the statements, from item 6 – 10, implying that the teaching of new technology provides Business Education students with good knowledge of ICT for teaching and learning; exposes them to acquire knowledge of new technology which provides the students with the basic foundation of information in becoming management technologists; new technology helps in providing fundamental understanding of the internet, and helps students to develop skills in becoming data analysts; knowledge about new technology helps students to use the latest technological machines; and new technology enables students to develop skills in the use of computer. All the items from 6-10 have mean values of 3.20, 3.12, 3.17, 3.01 and 3.11 respectively. This implies that the application of new technology influenced the career aspiration of Business Education students in higher institutions in Port Harcourt metropolis to a high extent. Also, the grand mean of 3.12 and 3.05 respectively, further shows that both respondents from the Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education accepted the fact that Business Education students employed new technology which influenced their career aspiration in the higher institutions in Port Harcourt metropolis to a high extent.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean rating of RSU and IAUE students on the extent to which the exploration of innovative ideas influence the career aspiration of Business Education students’ in higher institutions in Port Harcourt metropolis.

Table 3: Z-test Analysis of Difference between RSU and IAUE Respondents on the extent to which the exploration of Innovative Ideas influence the Career Aspiration of Business Education Students in Higher Institutions in Port Harcourt Metropolis

Status	N	Mean \bar{X}	Standard Deviation	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
RSU Students	140	3.07	0.83	1.29	1.96	Accepted
IAUE Students	425	3.01	0.87			

At the 0.05 level of significance, the study in Table 3 showed that the z-cal of 1.29 is smaller than the z-crit of 1.96. Because the computed z-value is less than the z-critical value, it is not statistically significant. Therefore, hypothesis 1 was approved with the finding that there is no discernible difference between the mean ratings of RSU and IAUE respondents regarding the degree to which business education students in higher education institutions in the Port Harcourt metropolis were influenced by the exploration of novel ideas in terms of their career aspirations.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the mean rating of RSU and IAUE Business education students on the extent to which the application of new technology influence the career aspiration of students' in higher institutions in Port Harcourt metropolis.

Table 4: Z-test Analysis of Difference between RSU and IAUE Respondents on the extent to which the Application of New Technology influence the Career Aspiration of Business Education Students in Higher Institutions in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Status	N	Mean \bar{x}	Standard Deviation	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
RSU Students	140	3.12	0.88	1.24	1.96	Accepted
IAUE Students	425	3.05	0.87			

Table 4's study showed that the z-crit of 1.96 is greater than the z-cal of 1.24. Because the estimated z-ratio is smaller than the specified critical value of z-ratio, it is not statistically significant at the 0.05 level of significance. As a result, hypothesis 2 is accepted, and the study's findings indicate that there is no discernible difference between RSU and IAUE Business Education students' mean ratings of how much the use of new technology has influenced students' career aspirations in Port Harcourt, Nigeria.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

In this study, research question one sought to find out the extent to which exploration of innovative ideas influence the career aspiration of Business Education students in higher institutions in Port Harcourt metropolis. The findings revealed that exploration of innovative ideas influenced the career aspiration of students in higher institutions in Port Harcourt metropolis to a high extent. The grand mean score of RSU and IAUE students of (3.07) and (3.01) respectively, showed that they accepted the fact that exploration of innovative ideas influenced the career aspiration of Business Education students in higher institutions in Rivers State to a high extent. The analysis also indicated that the respondents accepted the view that innovative ideas acquired from entrepreneurship education enables Business Education students to develop knowledge and skills for starting their own businesses; promotes new ideas among the students; gives them knowledge in solving problems in relationship management, among others. The findings are in consonance with the views of Gibb (2018) who observed that entrepreneurship education was always seeking solution to problems and taking new ideas. Similarly, the findings align with the study of Allen (2012) who submitted that entrepreneurship education had helped to educate and motivate students to acquire skills. In the same vein, the result of hypothesis one showed that the RSU and IAUE respondents were not significantly different in their perception on the extent to which exploration of innovative ideas influenced the career aspiration of Business Education students. This could probably be because they were taught using similar curriculum which made them to understand the importance of entrepreneurship education.

The result of research question two, sought to examine the extent to which application of new technology influenced the career aspiration of students in higher institutions in Port Harcourt metropolis. The findings indicated that the respondents accepted the statements that the teaching of new technology, provides Business Education students with good knowledge of ICT for teaching and learning; exposes them to acquire knowledge of new technology which provides the students with the basic foundation of information in becoming management technologists; new technology helps in providing fundamental understanding of the internet and helps students to develop skills in becoming data analysts, among others, to a high extent. The grand mean score of RSU and IAUE respondents of (3.12) and (3.05)

respectively, showed that the application of new technology influenced the career aspiration of Business Education students in higher institutions in Port Harcourt metropolis to a high extent. The findings of the study shares the same view with Begley (2017) who admitted that entrepreneurship education provides the students with the basic foundation of information management technology. Duck (2013) study also found that entrepreneurship education helped students to use latest technological machines. Furthermore, the second hypothesis indicated that respondents from the RSU and IAUE were not significantly different in their perception on the extent to which the application of new technology influenced the career aspiration of Business Education students in Port Harcourt metropolis. The outcome of this result may probably be related to their having a similar background.

Implications for Counselling

The counselling implication of the study is that using group counselling techniques, counsellors in higher institutions in Port Harcourt metropolis should encourage the students to develop essential skills that will empower them to make the right choices which will enhance their entrepreneurial success. Furthermore, using group counselling techniques, the counsellor may assist the students and their teachers in providing mentorship which will enable them to overcome challenges in the course of their training.

CONCLUSION

The importance of entrepreneurship education on career aspirations of students' in higher institutions in Rivers State cannot be over-emphasized. The study deduced that entrepreneurship education promoted exploration of innovative ideas; and encouraged the application of new technology among Business Education students in higher institutions in Port Harcourt metropolis. Hence, it helped students to develop skills in being creative and productive.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Lecturers teaching Business Education students should be versed in the knowledge of current innovations in their entrepreneurship education programmes in order to assist the students develop interest more in learning in order to promote more exploration of innovative ideas among the students.
2. The state Government should train more teachers and provide funds for more innovative programmes to increase the students' entrepreneurship knowledge and skills.

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